

Article

Neutrino Mass Spectrum for Co-Bimaximal Mixings from Quantum Gravity

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Abstract: We consider non-normalizable interaction term as a perturbation of the conventional neutrino mass matrix. Quantum gravitational (Planck scale) effects lead to an effective $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 Lagrangian involving neutrino and Higgs fields. On symmetry breaking, this operator gives rise to correction to the neutrino masses and mixing. The gravitational interaction $M_X = M_{pl}$ which gives rise to additional terms in neutrino mass matrix. We also assume that, just above the electroweak breaking scale, neutrino masses are nearly degenerate and their mixing is Co-bimaximal mixing by assuming mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0 = 10^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $\tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2} = 34^\circ$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \pm\frac{\pi}{2}$. There additional term can be considered to be perturbation of the GUT scale Co-bimaximal neutrino mass matrix. The relation consider with solar and atmospheric neutrino oscillation data predicted above GUT scale $m'_1 \cong 0.00001\text{eV} - 0.00003\text{eV}$, $m'_2 \cong 0.00008\text{eV} - 0.00012$, and $m'_3 \cong 0.000207\text{eV} - 000320\text{eV}$.

Keywords: Neutrino, Co-Bimaximal Mixings, Quantum Gravity

1. Introduction

The phenomenon of neutrino oscillation, impressive advance have been made to understand the phenomenology of neutrino oscillation through solar neutrino, atmospheric neutrino, reactor neutrino and accelerator neutrino experiments. These experiments enabling the determination of the Maki-Nakigawa Sakata (MNS) lepton mixing matrix. The main physical goal in future experiment are the

determination of the unknown parameter θ_{13} . In particular, the observation of δ is quite interesting from the point of view that δ related to the origin of the matter in the universe. CP violation is one of the most important problem in particle physics [1,2,3,4,5]. One of the most important parameter in neutrino physics is the magnitude of mixing angle θ_{13} and CP phase δ . The search for CP violation is great interest to various aspects of neutrino physics. At present information regarding θ_{13} , we have an upper bound that is bases on the CHOOZ experiment [6], that is $\theta_{13} \leq 13^\circ$ at 3 sigma. Solar and atmospheric neutrino oscillation are associated with the neutrino mass square differences $\Delta_{21} = m_2^2 - m_1^2$ and $\Delta_{31} = m_3^2 - m_1^2$ respectively. In analogy to the quark sector, θ_{12} is the $e - \mu$ mixing in the neutrino sector related to mass eigenstate as [7]

$$m_1^2 = \frac{\sin^4 \theta_{12}}{\cos 2\theta_{12}} \Delta_{21} \tag{1}$$

$$m_2^2 = \frac{\cos^4 \theta_{12}}{\cos 2\theta_{12}} \Delta_{21} \tag{2}$$

$$m_3^2 = \frac{\cos^4 \theta_{12}}{\cos 2\theta_{12}} \Delta_{21} + \Delta_{32} \tag{3}$$

The numerical dependence of two neutrino masses m_1 and m_2 on the mixing angle θ_{12} . In Ma[18], proposed a new mixing matrix which is known as Co-bimaximal mixing by assuming mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0 = 10^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $\tan \theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin^2 \theta_{13}}{2} = 34^\circ$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$. Additional effects, which modify the above predictions, must exist so that the final prediction are close to the experimental determined values. The main purpose of the paper is to study a possible relation between neutrino mixing and neutrino mass eigenstate above the GUT scale. In Section 2, we outline the neutrino mixing parameter above GUT scale. In Section 3, numerical results are given and section 4 is devoted to the conclusions.

2. Neutrino Oscillation Parameter above GUT Scale

The neutrino mass matrix is assumed to be generated by the see saw mechanism [8, 9, 10]. We assume that the dominant part of neutrino mass matrix arise due to GUT scale operators and the lead to Co-bimaximal mixing. The effective gravitational interaction of neutrino with Higgs field can be expressed as $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 operator [11],

$$L_{grav} = \frac{\lambda_{\alpha\beta}}{M_{pl}} (\psi_{A\alpha} \epsilon \psi_C) C_{ab}^{-1} (\psi_{B\beta} \epsilon_{BD} \psi_D) + h.c. \tag{4}$$

Here and everywhere we use Greek indices α, β for the flavor states and Latin indices i, j, k for the mass states. In the above equation $\psi_\alpha = (\nu_\alpha, l_\alpha)$ is the lepton doublet, $\phi = (\phi^+, \phi^0)$ is the Higgs doublet and $M_{pl} = 1.2 \times 10^{19} \text{GeV}$ is the Planck mass λ is a 3×3 matrix in a flavor space with each elements $O(1)$. The Lorentz indices' $a, b = 1, 2, 3, 4$ are contracted with the charge conjugation matrix C and the $SU(2)_L$ isospin indices' $A, B, C, D = 1, 2$ are contracted with $\epsilon = i\sigma_2$, $\sigma_m (m = 1, 2, 3)$ are the Pauli matrices. After spontaneous electroweak symmetry breaking the Lagrangian in Eq.(4.0) generated additional term of neutrino mass matrix

$$L_{mass} = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} \lambda_{\alpha\beta} \nu_\alpha C^{-1} \nu_\beta, \tag{5}$$

where $v = 174 \text{GeV}$ is the VEV of electroweak symmetric breaking. We assume that the gravitational interaction is "flavor blind" that is $\lambda_{\alpha\beta}$ is independent of α, β indices. Thus the Planck scale contribution to the neutrino mass matrix is

$$\mu\lambda = \mu \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \tag{6}$$

where the scale μ is

$$\mu = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} eV. \tag{7}$$

We take Eq.(6.0) as perturbation to the main part of the neutrino mass matrix, that is generated by GUT dynamics. To calculate the effects of perturbation on neutrino observables. The calculation developed in an earlier paper [13]. A natural assumption is that unperturbed (0^{th} order mass matrix) M is given by

$$\mathbf{M} = U^* \text{diag}(M_i) U^\dagger, \tag{8}$$

where, $U_{\alpha i}$ is the usual mixing matrix and M_i , the neutrino masses is generated by Grand unified theory. Most of the parameter related to neutrino oscillation are known, the major expectation is given by the mixing elements U_{e3} . We adopt the usual parametrization.

$$\frac{|U_{e2}|}{|U_{e1}|} = \tan\theta_{12}, \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{|U_{\mu3}|}{|U_{\tau3}|} = \tan\theta_{23}, \tag{10}$$

$$|U_{e3}| = \sin\theta_{13}. \tag{11}$$

In term of the above mixing angles, the mixing matrix is

$$U = \text{diag}(e^{if_1}, e^{if_2}, e^{if_3})R(\theta_{23})\Delta R(\theta_{13})\Delta^* R(\theta_{12})\text{diag}(e^{ia_1}, e^{ia_2}, 1). \tag{12}$$

The matrix $\Delta = \text{diag}(e^{\frac{i\delta}{2}}, 1, e^{-\frac{i\delta}{2}})$ contains the Dirac phase. This leads to CP violation in neutrino oscillation a_1 and a_2 are the so called Majoring phase, which effects the neutrino less double beta decay. f_1, f_2 and f_3 are usually absorbed as a part of the definition of the charge lepton field. Planck scale effects will add other contribution to the mass matrix that gives the new mixing matrix can be written as [10]

$$U' = U(1 + i\delta\theta),$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} U_{e1} & U_{e2} & U_{e3} \\ U_{\mu1} & U_{\mu2} & U_{\mu3} \\ U_{\tau1} & U_{\tau2} & U_{\tau3} \end{pmatrix} + i \begin{pmatrix} U_{e2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{e1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{e1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{e3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \\ U_{\mu2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\mu1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\mu1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{\mu3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \\ U_{\tau2}\delta\theta_{12}^* + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\tau1}\delta\theta_{12} + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^*, & U_{\tau1}\delta\theta_{13} + U_{\tau3}\delta\theta_{23}^* \end{pmatrix}. \tag{13}$$

Where $\delta\theta$ is a hermit ion matrix that is first order in μ [12]. The first order mass square difference $\Delta M_{ij}^2 = M_i^2 - M_j^2$, get modified [10] as

$$\Delta M_{ij}^{\prime 2} = \Delta M_{ij}^2 + 2(M_i \text{Re}(m_{ii}) - M_j \text{Re}(m_{jj})), \tag{14}$$

Where

$$m = \mu U^t \lambda U,$$

$$\mu = \frac{v^2}{M_{pl}} = 2.5 \times 10^{-6} eV.$$

The change in the elements of the mixing matrix, which we parametrized by $\delta\theta$ [10], is given by

$$\delta\theta_{ij} = \frac{iRe(m_{jj})(M_i + M_j) - Im(m_{jj})(M_i - M_j)}{\Delta M_{ij}^2}. \tag{15}$$

The above equation determine only the off diagonal elenumements of matrix $\delta\theta_{ij}$. The diagonal element of $\delta\theta_{ij}$ can be set to zero by phase invariance. Using Eq(13), we can calculate neutrino mixing angle due to Planck scale effects,

$$\frac{|U'_{e2}|}{|U'_{e1}|} = \tan\theta'_{12}, \tag{16}$$

$$\frac{|U'_{\mu3}|}{|U'_{\tau3}|} = \tan\theta'_{23}, \tag{17}$$

$$|U'_{e3}| = \sin\theta'_{13} \tag{18}$$

For degenerate neutrinos, $M_3 - M_1 \cong M_3 - M_2 \gg M_2 - M_1$, because $\Delta_{31} \cong \Delta_{32} \gg \Delta_{21}$. Thus, from the above set of equations, we see that U'_{e1} and U'_{e2} are much larger than U'_{e3} , $U'_{\mu3}$ and $U'_{\tau3}$. Hence we can expect much larger change in Δ_{21} [14] and θ_{12} compared to θ_{13} and θ_{23} [13]. As one can see from the above expression of mixing angle due to Planck scale effects, depends on new contribution of mixing matrix $U' = U(1 + i\delta\theta)$. The above statements are not dependent on the exact form of the matrix λ given in eq(6). They hold true for any form of λ , as long as all its elements are of order 1. New contribution of mixing following value of neutrino mass above GUT scale using Eq.(09) to Eq.(11)

$$m_1'^2 = \frac{\sin^4\theta'_{12}}{\cos 2\theta'_{12}} \Delta'_{21} \tag{19}$$

$$m_2'^2 = \frac{\cos^4\theta'_{12}}{\cos 2\theta'_{12}} \Delta'_{21} \tag{20}$$

$$m_3'^2 = \frac{\cos^4\theta'_{12}}{\cos 2\theta'_{12}} \Delta'_{21} + \Delta'_{32} \tag{21}$$

3. Numerical Results

We assume that, just above the electroweak breaking scale, the neutrino masses are nearly degenerate and the mixing are Co-bimaximal by assuming mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0 = 10^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $\tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin^2\theta_{13}}{2}$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \pm\frac{\pi}{2}$. Taking the common degenerate neutrino mass to be 2 eV,

which is the upper limit coming from tritium beta decay [15]. We compute the modified mixing angles using Eq. (19) to Eq.(21). We have taken $\Delta_{31} = 0.002\text{eV}^2$ [16] and $\Delta_{21} = 0.00008\text{eV}^2$ [17]. For simplicity we have set the charge lepton phases $f_1 = f_2 = f_3 = 0$. In table 1, we list the modified neutrino mixing angles and neutrino masses for some sample value of a_1 and a_2 . Due to Planck scale effects, only θ_{12} have reasonable deviation and θ_{23}, θ_{13} deviation is very small less than 0.3° [13]. From table1, we list the neutrino masses for Co-bimaximal mixing pattern $\theta_{13} \neq 0 = 10^\circ, \theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}, \tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \pm\frac{\pi}{2}$. In table1 and table 2, we have listed modified neutrino masses Vs reasonable range of Majorana phases.

Table 1: The modified neutrino mass square difference term for various value of phase. Input value are $\Delta_{31} = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2, \Delta_{21} = 8.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$ and Co-bimaximal mixing by assuming mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0 = 10^\circ, \theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}, \tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \frac{\pi}{2}$.

a1 in degrees	a2 in degrees	m1 in eV	m2 in eV	m3 in eV
0	0	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317
0	45	0.00003	0.00010	0.00302
0	90	0.00001	0.00008	0.00267
0	135	0.00002	0.00009	0.00277
0	180	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317
45	0	0.00003	0.00012	0.00303
45	45	0.00002	0.00011	0.00290
45	90	0.00001	0.00009	0.00262
45	135	0.00002	0.00010	0.00271
45	180	0.00002	0.00012	0.00303
90	0	0.00002	0.00011	0.00270
90	45	0.00001	0.00010	0.00263
90	90	0.00001	0.00009	0.00246
90	135	0.00001	0.00009	0.00251
90	180	0.00002	0.00011	0.00270
135	0	0.00002	0.00010	0.00276
135	45	0.00002	0.00009	0.00268
135	90	0.00002	0.00008	0.00248
135	135	0.00003	0.00009	0.00254

135	180	0.00004	0.00010	0.00276
180	0	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317
180	45	0.00001	0.00010	0.00302
180	90	0.00001	0.00008	0.00267
180	135	0.00003	0.00009	0.00277
180	180	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317

Table 2: The modified neutrino mass square difference term for various value of phase. Input value are $\Delta_{31} = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ eV}^2$, $\Delta_{21} = 8.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ eV}^2$ and Co-bimaximal mixing by assuming mixing angle $\theta_{13} \neq 0 = 10^\circ$, $\theta_{23} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $\tan\theta_{12}^2 = \frac{1-3\sin\theta_{13}^2}{2}$ and Dirac phase $\delta = \frac{-\pi}{2}$

a1 in degrees	a2 in degrees	m1 in eV	m2 in eV	m3 in eV
0	0	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317
0	45	0.00002	0.00009	0.00276
0	90	0.00001	0.00008	0.00267
0	135	0.00003	0.00010	0.00303
0	180	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317
45	0	0.00002	0.00010	0.00254
45	45	0.00001	0.00009	0.00249
45	90	0.00001	0.00008	0.00268
45	135	0.00001	0.00009	0.00276
45	180	0.00002	0.00010	0.00270
90	0	0.00002	0.00011	0.00270
90	45	0.00001	0.00010	0.00252
90	90	0.00001	0.00009	0.00247
90	135	0.00001	0.00010	0.00264
90	180	0.00002	0.00011	0.00270
135	0	0.00003	0.00012	0.00303
135	45	0.00002	0.00010	0.00270
135	90	0.00001	0.00009	0.00262
135	135	0.00003	0.00010	0.00309
135	180	0.00004	0.00011	0.00320

180	0	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317
180	45	0.00002	0.00009	0.00276
180	90	0.00001	0.00008	0.00267
180	135	0.00003	0.00010	0.00303
180	180	0.00003	0.00011	0.00317

4. Conclusions

We assume that the main part of neutrino masses and mixing arise from GUT scale operator. We considered these to be 0th order quantities. The gravitational interaction of lepton field with SM Higgs field give rise to a $SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ invariant dimension-5 effective Lagrangian give originally by Weinberg [11]. On electroweak symmetry breaking this operators leads to additional mass terms. We considered these to be perturbation of GUT scale mass terms. This model predicts the modified neutrino masses $m'_1 \cong 0.00001\text{eV} - 0.00003\text{eV}$, $m'_2 \cong 0.00008\text{eV} - 0.00012$, and $m'_3 \cong 0.000207\text{eV} - 0.000320\text{eV}$, which is corresponds to Planck scale $M_{\text{pl}} \approx 2.0 \times 10^{19}\text{GeV}$. In this paper, we studied how physics from planck scale effects the neutrino masses. We compute the modified neutrino mass eigenvalues due to the additional mass terms for the case of Co-bimaximal mixing. The change in Δ_{31} , due to these Planck scale correction are negligible. But the change in Δ'_{21} is enough that final value falls within the experimentally accepted region [19]. This occurs, of course for degenerate neutrino mass with a common mass of about 2eV.

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